

EJP SOIL
CARBONSEQ

Soil organic carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils in Europe

Deliverable 5.3

Assessment of SOC sequestration measures on other GHG emissions

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CH ₄	Methane
EF	Emission factor
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GJ	Gigajoule
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
IPCC	International Panel on Climate Change
LCA	life cycle assessment
LER	Land equivalent ratio
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
SD	Standard Deviation
SE	Standard Error
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SOM	Soil organic matter
SRC	Short rotation coppice

Executive summary

Soil organic carbon sequestration measures can contribute to climate change mitigation. Different measures have been proposed, however, there are still open questions related to the feasibility and effect of these measures. One of the questions is whether these measures can lead to a net reduction of GHG emissions in CO₂-equivalents or if there are also tradeoffs, for example due to increased fuel or fertilizer use. These potential tradeoffs related to the other GHG emissions when implementing soil carbon sequestration measures are addressed in this report.

The measures selected to investigate potential tradeoffs of SOC sequestration measures were no- and reduced tillage, land use change to energy crops (willow and miscanthus), cropland conversion to grassland, agroforestry, a change in crop rotation, cover crops, and incorporation of crop residues. Based on literature and expert knowledge we identified which farm operations change when a the SOC sequestration measure is applied. This included machinery use, production of inputs such as fertilizers or pesticides, and the indirect emissions related to the fertilizer application. Two baseline farms defined in the Nutri2Cycle project were used for the quantification of impacts. All emissions were recorded in kg CO₂-eq/ha. If numbers on consumption of fuel, electricity, or product were not available in this unit, conversion factors from literature were used. For the direct and indirect N₂O soil emissions, the emission factors from the IPCC guidelines were applied.

When comparing the average emissions per baseline farm, land use change to miscanthus had the highest reduction in emissions (more than 4 times lower emissions), followed by land use change to willow (almost two times lower emissions). For both, the high reduction is mainly due to the reduction in fossil energy use by using the biomass for energy production. The third highest reduction was found for adding a legume (alfalfa) to the crop rotation (42%), mainly due to the reduction in fertilizer need. Also for agroforestry the reduction in fertilizer use played a big role as well (19%). The addition of a cover crop could reduce NO₃ leaching substantially, leading to an overall reduction in GHG emissions of 5.4%. No- and reduced tillage only had minor reductions (2.8% and 2.2%, respectively) as the use of a tillage machinery only has a small contribution to the overall carbon balance. Two measures, land use change to grassland (12%) and incorporation of crop residues (37%), led to an increase in GHG emissions. The first because of an increased use of fertilizer. The second because straw could not be used for bioenergy production as was assumed in the baseline, which could increase GHG emissions from increased fossil energy use.

When soil organic carbon sequestration is taken into account, the order of emission reduction changes and land use change to miscanthus has the highest potential to reduce overall GHG emissions, followed by land use change to willow, cover crops, crop rotation, no till, agroforestry, land use change grassland, and reduced tillage, while crop residue incorporation had higher emissions compared to the baseline. Based on literature information, we also assessed whether there would be additional tradeoffs related to changes in crop yields and indirect land use changes (ILUC). This showed that some practices might have a risk on ILUC related emissions (no-till, reduced till and conversion to energy crops), while agroforestry has most benefits as it can potentially increase crop yields while also reducing GHG emissions.

1 Introduction

Agriculture can play an important role in climate change mitigation by sequestering carbon in soils. However, for European soils, a comprehensive assessment is missing on how much soil organic carbon (SOC) can be sequestered with different management practices. The EJP Soil CarboSeq project aims to quantify the feasible SOC sequestration potential for European agricultural soils. The CarboSeq project will determine the feasible SOC sequestration potential for a series of different SOC-sequestration measures. However, some management practices that increase SOC stocks may also have an impact on other GHG emissions, such as CH₄ and N₂O emissions (Guenet et al., 2021). It is therefore important to know the effects of these potential trade-offs, in order to prevent negative impacts of the SOC sequestration measures.

In Task 5.1 of the CarboSeq project, the potential impacts of SOC sequestration measures on N₂O emissions were assessed, as carbon and nitrogen dynamics in the soil are closely linked. The assessment was based on meta-analyses of existing literature, see Deliverable 5.1 (Porre et al., 2024). Besides these direct impacts on N₂O emissions, there can also be indirect effects on GHG emissions, because of changes in fuel use, fertilizer use and crop yields. For a complete overview of GHG impact of the SOC sequestration practices, it is important to also have insights in these indirect GHG effects.

The objective of this report is to provide a systematic assessment of the effect on GHG emissions in other parts of agricultural management (indirect emissions) of SOC sequestration measures. For each SOC sequestration measure the possible trade-offs will be systematically described. A simplified life cycle assessment will be used to quantify the effects on other GHG emissions for a default farming situation, especially those related to the use of fossil energy, but also effects of decreased or increased use of fertilizer will be accounted for.

2 SOC sequestration measures

In this study we included the following SOC sequestration measures, based on the work done in WP2 and WP4 of the CarboSeq project: no tillage, reduced tillage, agroforestry, adding a legume to the crop rotation, cover crops and crop residue incorporation. Their effect on carbon sequestration is further outlined in CarboSeq Deliverable WP2.1 (Panagea et al., 2023). In addition, we assessed the indirect emissions from land use change, from cropland to energy crops and cropland to grassland, which are both addressed in WP4 of CarboSeq. A change in grassland management was not considered as in WP4 insufficient literature was available to assess the impact on SOC. Also, organic amendments were left out, as this would mainly lead to a shift in emissions from one location to the other, as manure that is used more on one farm is no longer used at the other farm, possibly leading to an increased use in fertilizer there. In the following paragraphs the measures are shortly described. A detailed explanation of measures can be found in Panagea et al. (2023) and the upcoming Deliverable of WP4 of the CarboSeq project.

In CarboSeq the IPCC stock change approach is used to quantify the effects of the SOC sequestration measures. This relative stock change factor (dimensionless) was applied to estimate emission factors (EF) describing changes in SOC stocks. This relative EF indicates a relative change in SOC stocks in the management option under evaluation (treatment) compared to a reference stock.

2.1 Reduced and no tillage

Inversion tillage (conventional tillage) involves one-off inversion of agricultural soil to depths of up to 30 cm, while in reduced or non-inversion tillage the soil is not inverted or shallower depth. Zero or no tillage represents soil management in which the soil is never tilled. The loss of SOC in agricultural soils has often been assigned to tillage or ploughing of the soils, while less intensive tillage or non-inversion tillage could increase SOC content and improve soil health. However, it is often discussed that non-inversion tillage redistributes the organic matter in the soil profile rather than increasing overall SOC stocks (e.g. Haddaway et al., 2017). The most recent review of meta-analyses by Lessmann et al. (2022) confirmed the positive effects of non-inversion tillage on SOC stock increase in the upper layer (0-30 cm) finding a positive effect that varied from 0.07 to 0.31 t C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in the temperate climatic zone.

In CarboSeq an average EF of 1.03 (SE ±0.02) was determined for reduced tillage for the topsoil (0-30 cm) and for an average EF of 1.11 (SE ±0.03) was determined for no tillage. Although the EF for no tillage and reduced tillage were not statically significant, we still used the specific EFs in this report. Seidel et al. (2024) calculated a total European carbon potential for reduced tillage of 446 Mton CO₂ and 1574 Mton CO₂ over a period of 50 years. However, this only refer to the topsoil and possible losses of carbon in the subsoil are not taken into account in these estimates.

The meta-analysis from CarboSeq WP5 showed that reduced and no tillage increased N₂O emissions, with a median response ratio of 0.08 for reduced tillage and 0.15 for increased tillage. However, both response ratios were not significantly different from the control (conventional tillage). When looking at the raw mean difference there is a tendency for an increase in N₂O emissions when no- or reduced tillage is applied to the soil. Yet this increase is small and not significant (0.24-0.28 kg N₂O-N/ha).

2.2 Agroforestry

Agroforestry systems are defined as a combination of trees and crops or pasture grown in the same field (Cardinael et al., 2017). In well managed agroforestry systems a large part of the carbon returns to the soil in the form of roots exudates, crop residues and tree litter. Besides from this, a large amount of carbon is stored in the biomass. Due to the diversity of biogeographical regions in Europe, the variation of agroforestry systems is large, as these are adapted to local conditions (soil, climate, culture). A global meta-analysis showed that a land use change from grassland or cropland to agroforestry increased SOC stocks by 9.5% and 34% respectively (De Stefano & Jacobson, 2017). In CarboSeq WP2 an EF value for SOC stock change for both hedgerow and alley cropping systems of 1.26 (SD: ± 0.21 , SE: ± 0.05) is proposed. This value represents exclusively the area covered with woody elements, i.e., the area of the tree strip in alley-cropping systems.

Guenet et al. (2021) summarized that agroforestry systems are expected to reduce N_2O emissions due to lower soil moisture, increased soil porosity, increased nitrogen uptake by the trees and thus lower denitrification. Moreover, in temperate silvoarable systems tree rows are usually unfertilized and thus this automatically leads to lower N_2O emissions. A meta-analysis from 2016 that included all possible agroforestry systems worldwide showed a reduction in N_2O emissions of $2.7 \pm 10.6 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The meta-analysis from WP5 for European agroforestry systems showed that agroforestry systems reduced N_2O emissions, with a median response ratio of -0.77, which was statistically significant. When looking at absolute differences, using the “raw mean difference” method a non-significant reduction of $0.92 \text{ kg N}_2\text{O-N ha}^{-1}$ was found.

2.3 Adding legumes in the crop rotation

Crop diversification practices can include higher crop diversity, inclusion of legumes, growing more perennial crops, implementing temporal grassland (ley-crop-rotations), and/or mixed cropping. Crop diversification practices are expected to improve the productivity, yield stability, and resource use efficiency. Crop diversification practices that are expected to incorporate more C into plant biomass that may subsequently increase SOC stocks via increased C inputs can be diverse. Given the large variety in options, we limited the analysis to adding a leguminous crop to the crop rotation. This was also the main option investigated in WP2, as sufficient data was available, and increasing the share of leguminous crops is also high on the political agenda of the EU.

CarboSeq WP2 proposed the following regression equation for the estimation of EFs in the case of having an increased share of forage legumes in the cropping system:

$$EF = 1.182198 + 0.003957 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.129105 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$$

where “percentage difference” refers to additional fraction of fodder legumes in the rotation (%) compared to the control treatment. The *SOC of the control* ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is estimated by dividing the SOC of the control with the sampling depth. In general, an increase in SOC is expected in soils with lower SOC stocks and when a higher share of leguminous crops are grown.

As changes in crop rotations can be very diverse, and with large potential changes in fertilization, this measure was not investigated in WP5 for the effect on N₂O emissions. However, adding a leguminous crop to the rotation will reduce the need for nitrogen fertilizer and therefore decrease N₂O emissions. In the calculations for this report this effect was taken into account as further explained in Chapter 3.

2.4 Cover crops

The cultivation of cover crops is an effective management measure to increase the C-input to arable soils potentially increasing the SOC stocks. Cover crops, also named inter-crops, green manure or catch crops, are crops that replace bare fallow during winter period and are ploughed under as green manure before sowing of the next main crop. The advantage of cover crops as compared to other management practices that increase SOC is that they neither cause a decline in yields, like extensification, nor carbon losses in other systems, like organic manure applications may do (Poeplau and Don, 2015).

A meta-analysis by Poeplau and Don (2015) found an average SOC sequestration rate of 0.32 ton C/ha/year. In CarboSeq WP2 the long-term C sequestration potential by growing cover crops versus no cover crops was evaluated for European arable farming systems based on European LTEs. Based on their analysis one general EF for cover crops for Europe is proposed, i.e., 1.06 (SE ±0.02). The European wide carbon potential over 50 years of this measure (Seidel et al., 2024) is 208 Mton CO₂.

The analysis of CarboSeq WP5 on the effect of cover crops on N₂O emissions, showed that N₂O emissions on average increased, with a median response ratio of 0.46 and an absolute increase of 0.23 kg N₂O/ha/year. However, the variability was high, and the effect was not statistically significant. The high variability might be explained by differences in cover crop management, i.e. which cover crop species was used, was the cover crop fertilized and how was the cover crop terminated.

2.5 Incorporating crop residues

Crops add C to the soil via roots, root exudates, stubble and residues of above-ground biomass that is left on the field after harvest (crop residues). If these crop residues such as cereal straw are removed from a field, e.g., for energy production, animal feeding or bedding and not returned, this source of organic C is lost for this specific field. Incorporating the crop residues instead can increase SOC stocks of arable soils. In addition, retaining above-ground crop residues can improve soil structure, reduce bulk density and improve the infiltration rate in soils.

CarboSeq WP2 proposed the following regression equation for calculation the EF for crop residue:

$$EF = 1.114560 - 0.075746 * SOC \text{ of the control per cm (Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) + 0.214673 * \text{crop rotation (\%)} + 0.002988 * \text{Clay content (\%)} - 0.000147 * \text{annual rainfall (mm)}$$

The EFs indicate that management systems with retention of crop residues show higher SOC stocks after a certain number of experimental years than when residues are removed. The positive effect on SOC stocks is higher for soils still low in SOC, for crop rotations with more cereals, for soils with a higher

clay content and for drier regions. The European wide carbon potential over 50 years of this measure (Seidel et al., 2024) is 437 Mton CO₂.

2.6 Land use change

For land use change measures we include three different land use changes: conversion of cropland to grassland and conversion of cropland to energy crops, using both miscanthus and willow as perennial energy crops.

A land use change to woody vegetation has the potential to increase the SOC stock European wide by 97 Mton CO₂ over 50 years (Seidel et al., 2024).

The meta-analysis from WP5 for land use changes showed that cropland conversion to perennial energy crops and grassland reduced N₂O emissions. However, the number of studies was very limited. For cropland to energy crops the median response ratio was -2.57 and for cropland to grassland -3.04. These values are statistically significantly different from the control (no land use change), but given the low number of studies, the values should be used with care. When the land use change effects were expressed in raw mean difference the median was close to zero, but the variation was very large considering the small amount of data available.

3 Methodology

3.1 Literature research

To assess the indirect GHG emissions following a change in crop/soil management, a literature research was carried out. We looked for literature that reported emissions from farm operations or in which a life cycle assessment (LCA) of one of the practices was conducted. From these studies, the possible changes in farm operations were used as a starting point for the analysis as well as possible changes in NO₃-leaching which might increase or decrease the indirect N₂O emissions. Not all possible changes were taken into account, if there was not enough evidence of the effect of a measure, the specific factor was left out. Furthermore, a simplified calculation of carbon stock changes was done to assess potential reduction or increase in soil emissions from these measures.

3.2 Baseline

To quantify possible changes, a baseline was necessary. To this end, we selected a typical farming situations, for which we used information from a selected baseline farm that was developed in the EU Nutri2Cycle project (Duan et al., 2021). This farm was simulated using the process-based Daisy model. The following information was available: crop rotation, fertilizer amount, NO₃-leaching, and amount of straw removed from the field (Table 1). The information on pesticide use was not available. For that aspect we used national reports that countries need to provide to Eurostat about the pesticide use in their country.

The Nutri2Cycle baseline farm Vredepeel from the Netherlands was selected. This farm represents arable land management in the Atlantic Central region (Duan et al., 2021). The crop rotation consisted of consumption potatoes, silage maize, sugar beet and winter wheat. For plant protection products, data from the national statistical office (CBS) were used (CBS, 2022). The use in kg active compound per ha were extracted for 2016 for the pesticide groups herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides. For the calculation of changes in grassland management, the Dutch dairy farm Cranendonck was chosen, and the information provided for grassland was taken from Duan et al. (2018) and CBS (2022) for the use of pesticides (Table 1).

Table 1: Crop rotation with fertilizer, pesticides, N leaching and straw yield for the arable baseline farm. NO₃ leaching and straw yield were calculated out of the 60 year average from model simulations with Daisy.

Crop	Mineral fertilizer [kg N/ha]	Slurry [kg N/ha]	Herbicide [kg/ha]	Fungicide [kg/ha]	Insecticide [kg/ha]	NO ₃ -leaching [kg N/ha]	Straw yield [t/ha]
Silage maize	138	60	1.1	0	0	42	-
Potato	142	140	3.7	8.2	0.2	53	-
Sugar beet	142	70	3.4	0.4	0	79	-
Winter wheat	150	-	0.4	0.6	0	100	4.0
Perennial ryegrass	184	165	0.5	0.2	0	10	-

3.3 Field operations

3.3.1 General

For this report, a simplified farming year is considered. In spring, tillage is done to prepare the field for the crop. This includes ploughing with a moldboard and stubble cultivation. Also, pesticides are applied twice, which comprised herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides depending on the crop type. Subsequently, the crop is planted/sown and fertilizers are applied, all crops receive twice a mineral N fertilizer and most also receive slurry (Table 1) in one application. Due to the addition of nitrogen to the soil, N₂O is emitted from the soil, which was calculated according to the IPCC guidelines. Also, NH₃ is volatilized, leading to indirect N₂O emissions. At the end of the growing season the crop is harvested, and in the case of cereals, the straw is removed from the field. We assumed in the baseline that straw is transported to a biogas or combined heat and power plant, distance of 50 km, to produce heat and/or electricity. During the growing season, NO₃ leaching can already occur, however, in winter, NO₃ leaching might be aggravated as there is no crop to take the excess N from the soil.

3.3.2 Measure specific changes in field operations

3.3.2.1 Cover crops

When cover crops are grown in the field, an extra crop is added to the system, requiring extra field operations. Cover crops increase the machinery use as the field needs to be prepared for the seeds (Plaza-Bonilla et al., 2018), for which an extra application of the field cultivator was considered here. Furthermore, the production of seeds needs to be taken into account. In some of the Nutri2Cycle baseline farms, fodder radish is used as a cover crop (Duan et al., 2021) and the advised amount of seeds is 12.5 kg/ha (Cotswold Seeds, 2024). The cover crop doesn't receive extra fertilization and also no herbicide is applied. Tillage is done the next spring but is not seen as an extra emission as it is done independently of the cover crop to prepare the field for the subsequent crop. As cover crops might change the NO₃ leaching, literature was searched to find the relative effect of the cover crop.

3.3.2.2 Cropland to energy crops

If a land use change takes place, some of the farm operations decrease in frequency, but also other machinery needs to be used and different amounts of fertilizers and pesticides are applied. In this assessment, a land use change to willow, miscanthus, or grassland is considered. It was decided to focus on the short rotation coppice (SRC) willow and miscanthus for the energy crops, which are often mentioned in literature (e.g., Clarke et al., 2019; Harris et al., 2015). A comparison of these systems with cropland in Ireland was done by Clarke et al. (2019). As such a complete overview of farm operations was not found in other studies, we decided to take their study as a reference for the changes. The change in frequency of operations is given in Table 2. The different land uses further require different machinery for planting and harvest per application. The planting and harvest machine for arable crops uses 3.8 kg fuel/ha and 33.3 kg fuel/ha, respectively, while it is for willow 8.9 kg fuel/ha and 84 kg fuel/ha, and for miscanthus 8.9 kg fuel/ha and 6.2 kg fuel/ha. These numbers are then multiplied by the frequency to convert them to yearly emissions. Willow has a life cycle of 22 years and miscanthus of 17 years.

Table 2: Frequency of operations in one year. Willow has a life cycle of 22 years and miscanthus of 17 years. Therefore, the frequency of one operation in the life cycle is divided by 22 and 17 respectively.

Field operation	Arable crops	Willow	Miscanthus
Ploughing	1	$2/22 = 0.09$	$2/17 = 0.12$
Stubble cultivation	1	$1/22 = 0.05$	$1/17 = 0.06$
Planting	1	$1/22 = 0.05$	$1/17 = 0.06$
Fertilizer application	2	$7/22 = 0.32$	$14/17 = 0.82$
Pesticide application	2	$8/22 = 0.36$	$15/17 = 0.88$
Harvest	1	$7/22 = 0.32$	$14/17 = 0.82$

The amount of fertilizer is not the same either. If 100% of fertilizer is used for the crop in a year, this is 17.4 % for willow and 32.8 % for miscanthus. For pesticides, willow receives 7.7 % of the yearly amount for cropland, miscanthus 17.4 %. For the NO₃ leaching, the same numbers as modelled for grassland are used.

Energy crops can be used to produce heat and electricity. Here, literature is searched to find the emissions to produce energy from fossil sources (in kg CO₂-eq/ha) which can be replaced by willow and miscanthus. For this, transportation needs to be considered too. The same numbers as for the transport of straw will be used for this purpose. Furthermore, energy or heat can only be produced when the crops are harvested, therefore, the amount of fossil energy emissions replaced will be multiplied by the frequency of harvest.

3.3.2.3 Cropland to grassland

As it seems unlikely, that an arable farmer changes their whole crop rotation to permanent grassland, a change of silage maize to temporal grassland (ryegrass) is considered here. Ryegrass was chosen because it is also used on the Dutch dairy baseline farm (Duan et al., 2021). Besides the changes due to the characteristics of the farming system (Table 1), it is also assumed that pesticide spraying only takes place once in contrast to the double spraying in the crop baseline.

3.3.2.4 Agroforestry

As already discussed in WP2 of this project (Panagea et al., 2023), many different agroforestry systems exist. The kind of crops and trees can vary, the distance between trees or shrubs, as well as the agriculture to forest ratio on one hectare. The distance is also depending on the kind of machinery that is used in the respective system (Graves et al., 2009). Studies on agroforestry are still limited (Panagea et al., 2023). Dupraz et al. (2005) investigated an agroforestry system based on tree rows, which provided relevant information for this report. Willow was used as perennial crop in the tree row to make it comparable to the emissions calculated for the land use change practice. As Dupraz et al. (2005) report that a plantation of 10% would not have a negative influence on the farm economics, it was assumed that trees take up a space of 3 m while the cropland takes 27 m, which is in line with the recommended distance from the SAFE project.

For 90% of the farmland, farm operations do not change, however, they do change for the 10% where willow is planted. This means that overall, the amount of herbicide and pesticides applied changes as the area of cropland is reduced, while willow requires less fertilizer and herbicides compared to arable

crops (Clarke et al., 2019; Rigueiro-Rodríguez et al., 2009). For willow, the same machinery and frequencies are used as presented in 3.3.2.2. This means for the consumption of fuel, pesticides, and fertilizers:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consumption} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}} \right) &= \text{cropland consumption} \times 0.9 \times \text{frequency cropland} \\
 &+ \text{willow consumption } c \times 0.1 \times \text{frequency willow}
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, there can be a reduction of NO₃-leaching (Rigueiro-Rodríguez et al., 2009) which is taken into account by using the same NO₃ leaching values for the 10% tree area as is used for willow (section 3.3.2.2).

3.3.2.5 Crop rotation

In WP2, the authors looked at an increased share of legumes in the crop rotation. Therefore, a change in crop rotation to legumes was assessed here as well. For the arable farm, silage maize is replaced by alfalfa. Alfalfa is a two-year crop, meaning that the crop rotation changes from four to five years, posing challenges in comparing the average emissions between measures. To tackle this problem, emissions which occur only once in the two years are divided by 2. Tillage, pesticide use, planting, fertilizer application, and harvest only occur once in the two-year crop life. Emissions which occur every year, i.e. NO₃-leaching, are only filled in for one year. This way, the emissions for alfalfa are simulated for one cropping year.

Alfalfa was found to reduce NO₃-N stocks by 55% compared to corn (Singh et al., 2023). Therefore, in this assessment it is assumed that NO₃-leaching is 45% of the leaching under silage maize in the baseline farm. No information on alfalfa pesticide use was available in the CBS dataset, therefore, the same use as for grass was assumed. According to the literature, alfalfa has a N replacement potential of 100-200 kg/ha (Julier et al., 2017). Here, an N replacement of 100 kg/ha was used which is subtracted from the amount of mineral N fertilizer for the subsequent crop. Furthermore, no N fertilization of the alfalfa takes place, as this is often not done for leguminous crops (Hakl et al., 2014; Smith & Moore, 2020).

3.4 GHG emission calculations

3.4.1 For farm operations

To calculate GHG emissions in CO₂-eq, for most operations the paper from Lal (2004) was used (Table 3). The author gives carbon emission coefficients to convert kg of fuel or energy units such as kWh to kg C equivalents (C-eq). Numbers from Lal (2004) were used for the fuel related emissions of field operations and to convert the pesticide production from amount of product to emissions. Kg C-eq values were transformed to kg CO₂-eq by multiplying kg C-eq by 44/12. For fertilizer production emissions, numbers from Brentrup et al. (2018) were taken. The mean of the emissions in kg CO₂-eq/kg product were taken for ammonium nitrate and calcium ammonium nitrate, and converted to kg CO₂-eq/kg N by dividing by their N content.

3.4.2 N₂O soil emissions

3.4.2.1 Direct fertilization emissions

When fertilizer is applied, part of the added N is released to the atmosphere as N₂O. The IPCC guidelines (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019) provide default emission factors for N additions of 0.01. For wet climates, this factor is higher, namely 0.016, while dry climates have an emission factor of 0.005. The Netherlands have a wet climate and therefore the first emission factor was used. N₂O is a 265 times more powerful greenhouse gas than CO₂ (IPCC, 2014), thus, to convert it to kg CO₂-eq, it needs to be multiplied by this global warming potential. As the result from the emission factor calculation has the unit kg N₂O-N/kg N, this needs to be multiplied by 1.57 (44/28) in order to come to the unit kg N₂O.

$$\text{Direct fertilizer N}_2\text{O} = \text{Total N application} \times 0.016 \times 1.57 \times 265$$

3.4.2.2 Indirect fertilization emissions

Nitrogen fertilization also leads to indirect N₂O emissions, through NO₃ leaching and NH₃ volatilization. To account for this, the IPCC guidelines (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019) provide a default emission factor of 0.011 for NO₃ leaching from agricultural soils. The amount of NO₃ leaching is taken from the baseline simulation (Duan et al., 2018). For willow and miscanthus, the same leaching fraction as for grass was assumed.

For NH₃, there are two separate emission factors for slurry and different mineral fertilizers. Here, the factor for ammonium nitrate was taken. According to Hergoualc'h et al. (2019), slurry application releases 21% of the applied N as NH₃ to the atmosphere, and ammonium nitrate fertilizer 5%. From this NH₃, 1.4% is transformed to N₂O in wet climates. Thus, the indirect emissions through fertilization (in kg CO₂-eq/ha) are calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Indirect Fertilizer N}_2\text{O} &= (\text{NO}_3 \text{ leaching} \times 0.011) \\ &+ (\text{Mineral N application} \times 0.05 + \text{Slurry N application} \times 0.21) \times 0.014 \times 1.57 \\ &\times 265 \end{aligned}$$

Where the first part of the equation is the N₂O emission from NO₃ leaching and the second part the N₂O emission from NH₃ volatilization. The number 1.57 is used to convert from N₂O-N to N₂O and 265 is used to convert the N₂O emissions to CO₂-eq.

3.5 Calculation of the total indirect GHG emissions

The indirect GHG emissions per field operation and crop were listed in a spreadsheet for each measure. Subsequently, the emissions were summarized by taking the mean of each operation in the crop rotation. Based on this, the different measures could be compared for an average year.

3.6 Carbon sequestration

As outlined in chapter 2, the CarboSeq project proposed several stock change factors for the different measures. To calculate the potential carbon sequestration based on local circumstances of our baseline farm, RothC was used instead of these emission factors for crop rotation, residues, cover crops, and land use change to grassland and miscanthus. The change to miscanthus is modelled by assuming grassland for each year of the crop rotation with the same input as grass. Carbon

sequestration depends on the initial C content. In order to reflect this, we calculated the carbon balance for three different initial C contents, based on data from the baseline farm of the Nutri2Cycle project (Duan et al., 2018). For that baseline farm three different initial C contents were modelled, based on the 25th (1.7%), 50th (2.2%), and 75th (2.9%) quantile of the topsoil C in the region. Clay content at the baseline location is 0% as it was a sandy soil. An N content of 4.88 kg N/t fresh cattle slurry was taken to obtain the total amount of organic manure applied to the soil. The model was run for 50 years since also for the emission factors in WP8 this time period was taken.

RothC cannot be applied to simulate the tillage practices or woody elements. For these practices the emission factors from Seidel et al. (2024) were used here. These are 1.03 for reduced tillage, 1.11 for zero tillage, and 1.26 for woody biomass (here willow and agroforestry). For agroforestry, the emission factor only is applicable to the area covered by woody elements. A 10% cover of the area is assumed here.

RothC carbon sequestration and emission outputs are per ha. Also for the emission factors topsoil C stocks per ha are needed. The initial C content of the soil (in %) is converted to t C/ha by multiplying the initial C content by the depth (25cm) and the bulk density (1.3 g cm⁻³). The absolute change compared to the baseline can be calculated with the EF by the following formula:

$$Change [kgCO_2 ha^{-1}yr^{-1}] = \frac{(EF - 1) \times initial\ SOC [tCO_2 ha^{-1}] \times 3.7 \times 1000}{50yr}$$

To calculate the emissions from the soil, the baseline as modelled by RothC is also used for the measures which were calculated for the emission factors.

4 Results

The changes found in the literature review are presented in section 4.1. A comparison between the different measures is done in section 4.2. In section 4.3 the calculated carbon sequestration potential is presented. In Appendix A, the conversions to get to these emissions are displayed. Here, an overview of CO₂-eq/ha for the products and field operations is provided (Table 3) which were used to assess the carbon footprint of each measure.

Table 3: Emissions per field operation or emission source

Field operation / emission source	Crop	Emissions (kg CO ₂ -eq/ha)	Source
Default crop seeding	Default	11.7	1
Crop harvest	Default	115	1
Fertilization N ₂ O	Maize	1319	4, 6
Fertilization N ₂ O	Potato	1879	4, 6
Fertilization N ₂ O	Sugar beet	1412	4, 6
Fertilization N ₂ O	Wheat	999	4, 6
Fertilization N ₂ O	Grass	2325	4, 6
Min. fertilizer application	Default	3.3	1
Slurry application S	Default	27.9	1
Min. fertilizer production	Maize	478	4, 10
Min. fertilizer production	Potato	491	4, 10
Min. fertilizer production	Sugar beet	491	4, 10
Min. fertilizer production	Wheat	519	4, 10
Min. fertilizer production	Grass	637	4, 10
Fungicide	Maize	0.0	3, 1
Fungicide	Potato	117	3, 1
Fungicide	Sugar beet	5.7	3, 1
Fungicide	Wheat	8.6	3, 1
Fungicide	Grass and alfalfa	2.9	3, 1
Bioenergy production	Wheat	-2841	4, 7
Bioenergy production	Miscanthus	-7625	9, 7
Bioenergy production	Willow	-2119	9, 7
Herbicide	Maize	25.4	3, 1
Herbicide	Potato	85.5	3, 1
Herbicide	Sugar beet	78.5	3, 1
Herbicide	Wheat	9.2	3, 1
Herbicide	Grass and alfalfa	11.6	3, 1
Insecticide	Maize	0.0	3, 1
Insecticide	Potato	3.7	3, 1
Insecticide	Sugar beet	0.0	3, 1
Insecticide	Wheat	0.0	3, 1
Insecticide	Grass and alfalfa	0.0	3, 1
Miscanthus harvest	Miscanthus	17.7	2, 1
Miscanthus planting	Miscanthus	1.8	2, 1

Field operation / emission source	Crop	Emissions (kg CO ₂ -eq/ha)	Source
Moldboard plough	Default	55.7	2, 1
NO ₃ leaching	Maize	195	4, 6
NO ₃ leaching	Potato	243	4, 6
NO ₃ leaching	Sugar beet	363	4, 6
NO ₃ leaching	Wheat	460	4, 6
NO ₃ leaching	Grass	45.8	4, 6
No-till crop planting	Default	13.9	1, 1
Pesticide application	Default	5.1	1, 1
Seed production	Default	5.5	5, 11
Silage harvest	Silage	20.7	2, 1
Straw removal	Wheat	16.7	1
Straw transport	Wheat	8.8	4, 1, 8
Stubble cultivation	Default	14.7	1
Willow harvest	Willow	92.1	2, 1
Willow planting	Willow	1.4	2, 1
Vol. N ₂ O min. fert.	Maize	40.2	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O min. fert.	Potato	41.4	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O min. fert.	Sugar beet	41.4	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O min. fert.	Wheat	43.7	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O min. fert.	Grass	53.6	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O slurry	Maize	17.5	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O slurry	Potato	40.8	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O slurry	Sugar beet	20.4	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O slurry	Wheat	0.0	4, 6
Vol. N ₂ O slurry	Grass	48.1	4, 6

[1] (Lal, 2004), [2] (Clarke et al., 2019), [3] CBS Nederland, [4] (Duan et al., 2018), [5] (Plaza-Bonilla et al., 2018), [6] (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019), [7] (Slier et al., 2022), [8] (Timonen et al., 2019), [9] (Styles & Jones, 2008), [10] (Brentrup et al., 2018), [11] (Cotswold Seeds, 2024).

4.1 Changes for each SOC sequestration measure

4.1.1 No till

Overall, no till reduces the carbon footprint by 2.8%. The main changes identified for a change from a conventional tillage to a zero tillage system were the absence of a tillage machine and field cultivator, and the use of a different planting machine (e.g., Lal, 2004; Sørensen et al., 2014). While the first would decrease the emissions considerably (from 55.7 kg CO₂-eq/ha to 0 kg CO₂-eq/ha for ploughing and 14.7 kg CO₂-eq/ha for field cultivation, Table 4), the last could lead to a slight increase in emissions as a no-till planting machine requires more fuel (Table 3).

Furthermore, many authors expect an increased use in herbicides, as mechanical weed removal is not possible anymore. However, this increase is judged differently by different authors. While for example Lal (2004) or Hobbs & Govaerts (2010) report an increased use but do not provide numbers, in other studies herbicides are only applied in the no-till system (Dachraoui & Sombrero, 2020; Troccoli et al., 2015). Sainju et al. (2014) on the other hand make no difference in herbicide use in their study. This ambiguity in the literature was also noted by the authors of a Danish study who wanted to compare

energy inputs in different tillage systems (Sørensen et al., 2014). As a result, they conducted a survey amongst Danish farmers and based on this calculated a percentage of pesticide use for the different systems. They found an increase in herbicide use of 33% in no-tillage systems compared to conventional tillage, resulting in higher CO₂-eq/ha emissions for this product (Table 4). This increase by 16.4 kg CO₂-eq/ha is nevertheless much lower than the avoided emissions for the tillage operations.

4.1.2 Reduced tillage

Reduced tillage has a slightly lower but comparable reduction in CO₂-eq/ha emissions, namely 2.2%. This reduction is because of the abolishment of ploughing in reduced tillage systems. Instead, a field cultivator is used to prepare the soil, which has lower emissions compared to ploughing (Table 3). This reduction is despite that a different seeding machine than for the baseline is necessary (Sørensen et al., 2014), which has a higher fuel demand and thus emissions. Furthermore, an increase in herbicide use takes place, 27% increase according to Sørensen et al. (2014). Both lead to an increase in emissions, however, the reduced ploughing has the main effect and therefore there is a decrease in overall GHG emissions (Table 4).

4.1.3 Land use change

4.1.3.1 Cropland conversion to energy crops

Energy crops showed the highest reduction in CO₂-eq/ha emissions relative to the baseline farms. A reduction of 80% for willow and 70% for miscanthus was calculated, because of reduced frequency in field operations and use of fertilizers and pesticides (Table 4). Furthermore, as the name suggest, these crops can be used to produce electricity and heat. According to Styles & Jones (2008), 1 ha of miscanthus can produce 191 GJ/year and 1 ha of SRC willow 136 GJ/year. Slier et al. (2022) state that 1 GJ of natural gas releases 48.7 kg CO₂-eq. Thus, miscanthus can compensate 9297 kg CO₂-eq natural gas per ha and year, SRC willow 6620 kg CO₂-eq natural gas per ha every year. Here, every year where miscanthus or willow are harvested is considered, thus, in this assessment miscanthus replaces 7625 kg CO₂-eq/ha every year and willow 2119 kg CO₂-eq/ha every year (Table 3). When this is considered, willow has a reduction of 186% compared to the baseline, and miscanthus 467% compared to the baseline (Table 4).

4.1.3.2 Cropland conversion to grassland

On the arable farm, silage maize is replaced by perennial ryegrass. This land use change increased greenhouse gas emissions by 9% (Table 4). This is mainly related to the increased use of fertilizer for ryegrass compared to silage maize (Table 1). This increase could not be compensated by a decreased use of pesticides (only applied once for grass but applied twice for crop). NO₃ leaching decreases under grass (Table 1), however, the reduction in indirect emissions compared to the baseline is relatively low because of the higher NH₃ volatilization from fertilization (Table 3).

4.1.4 Agroforestry

Agroforestry can have a mitigating effect on the indirect emissions, decreasing them by 19%. Part of the decrease is due to the fact that many field operations need to be done on a smaller area and that less fertilizer is needed, together leading to an emission reduction of 8.1%. Another part is the replacement of natural gas by harvested biomass from the trees. Even though the trees only occupy

10% of the area, the mean compensation throughout the crop rotation is still higher than if only straw is used to produce heat or electricity (Table 4).

4.1.5 Crop rotation

In the arable crop rotation, silage maize is replaced by alfalfa, decreasing the overall emissions by 40% (Table 4). Since alfalfa is a two-year crop, this crop rotation comprises 5 years instead of the 4 years in the baseline. This reduces the emissions for field operations as tillage, pesticide application, planting, and harvest are only done once, and nitrogen fertilizer is not applied. However, the reduced mineral fertilizer use has a larger effect, as alfalfa does not require nitrogen fertilizer and the next crop (potato in the arable crop rotation) requires 100 kg N less compared to the baseline. This does not only decrease the emissions related to the production of fertilizer, but also has a large effect on direct and indirect N₂O emissions from the field (Table 4). For this SOC sequestration measure, only the use of fungicides increases, however, this increase in GHG emissions is only minor.

4.1.6 Cover crops

Cover crops increase the machinery use as the field needs to be prepared with a field cultivator for the cover crop seeds, and an additional field operation for seeding is required. Furthermore, extra seeds need to be produced (Table 4). Nevertheless, emissions are reduced by 5.4%. This is due to a decrease in NO₃ leaching under cover crops. In a study in Denmark, Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. (2022) found for fodder radish a reduction of 80-84% in a long term field experiment. Since this was only one study, it was decided to take numbers from meta-analyses in order to not overestimate the effect of cover crops. In a review of meta studies done in the EJP Soil TraceSoils project, a reduction ranging between 43% and 70% with a median of 53% and mean of 55% for non-leguminous crops was found (Velthof et al., in prep.). Thapa et al. (2018) conducted a meta-analysis and found a reduction of 56%. As this is very close to the mean reduction found in the TraceSoils analysis and they based this on a high number of observations (216), this number was chosen. This reduction has a big effect on the overall emissions (Table 4).

4.1.7 Crop residues incorporation

In literature it was found that the use of straw for bioenergy can compensate 711 kg CO₂-eq/t straw for natural gas (Slier et al., 2022). If straw is left on the field, this potential compensation will not occur anymore, leading to higher emissions of the whole crop rotation. Furthermore, the straw needs to be incorporated, with additional emissions from the field cultivator. Here an increase by 37% relative to the baseline was found (Table 4), even though several aspects of this measure could reduce some sources of GHG emissions. When leaving straw on the field, a straw baler is not necessary anymore and the straw does not need to be transported, resulting in a reduction in field operation emissions (Table 3). Another benefit of crop residues is the better N retention, which can decrease NO₃ leaching. Li et al. (2021) found in a global meta-analysis that crop residues could reduce NO₃ leaching by 14%. Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. (2022) found an average reduction of 25%, however, this effect was not statistically significant. For the calculations in this report, we used the numbers from Li et al. (2021), leading to reduced field emissions. Both emission reductions were not sufficient to compensate for the fact that straw was no longer used to replace natural gas. If the compensation of emissions from natural gas was not taken into account, emissions could be decreased relative to the baseline by 0.7%. This minor decrease is because of the saved indirect emissions, the emissions from straw removal and

transport are almost equalled out by the higher emissions from stubble cultivation to incorporate the straw (Table 4).

Table 4: GHG emissions (in kg CO₂-eq/ha) for different farm operations for each measure. Orange cells indicates a higher emission relative to the baseline, blue cells a lower emission.

Operation	Baseline	No tillage	Red. tillage	LUC willow	LUC misc.	LUC grass	Agro-forestry	Cover crop	Crop rotation	Crop residue
N ₂ O soil emissions	1379	1379	1379	240	455	1631	1263	1379	883	1379
Indirect N ₂ O emissions	376	376	376	64	79	350	345	251	325	360
Min fertilizer application	6.6	6.6	6.6	1	2.7	6.6	6	6.6	4.9	6.6
Slurry application	21	21	21	6.7	17	21	19	21	14	21
Harvest	115	115	115	92	18	91	112	115	100	115
Planting	15	17	17	1.4	1.8	12	14	24	14	15
Pesticide spraying	10	10	10	1.9	4.5	9	9.4	10	9	10
Ploughing	56	0	0	5.1	6.6	56	51	567	49	56
Stubble cultivation	15	0	15	0.7	0.9	15	13	26	13	18
Straw removal	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	0
Transport	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.8	7.2	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.2	0
Fungicide	33	33	33	2.5	5.7	34	30	33	33	33
Herbicide	50	66	63	3.8	8.6	46	46	50	45	50
Insecticide	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.1	0.2	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
M fertilizer production	495	495	495	86	163	535	453	495	289	495
Seed production	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1	0	0
Energy production	-710	-710	-710	-2119	-7625	-710	-851	-710	-710	0
Total	1868	1816	1828	-1607	-6849	2102	1519	1766	1075	2560
Total without energy prod.	2579	2526	2538	512	775	2813	2370	2477	1785	2560
Relative change (%)		-2.8	-2.2	-186	-467	12	-19	-5.4	-42	37
Relative change without energy prod.		-2.0	-1.6	-80	-70	9.1	-8.1	-3.9	-31	-0.7

4.2 Comparison of changes per emission source

To visualize the changes better and to see which kind of emissions have a big influence, the emissions per field operation / emission source are separated into groups and subgroups (Table 5).

Table 5: Operations with related subgroups and groups of emission sources.

Group	Subgroup	Field operation / emission source
Bioenergy production	Bioenergy production	Bioenergy production
Soil N ₂ O emissions	Direct and indirect soil N ₂ O emissions	Fertilization N ₂ O
Soil N ₂ O emissions	Direct and indirect soil N ₂ O emissions	NO ₃ leaching
Fuel consumption	Field preparation	Ploughing
Fuel consumption	Field preparation	Stubble cultivation
Fuel consumption	Crop management	Planting
Fuel consumption	Crop management	Min. fertilizer application
Fuel consumption	Crop management	Pesticide spraying
Fuel consumption	Crop management	Slurry application
Fuel consumption	Crop management	Harvest
Fuel consumption	Residue management	Straw removal
Fuel consumption	Residue management	Transport
Production of input	Pesticide production	Herbicide
Production of input	Pesticide production	Fungicide
Production of input	Pesticide production	Insecticide
Production of input	Fertilizer production	Min. fertilizer production
Production of input	Seeds	Seed production

For the groups, field emissions have the biggest influence on the overall carbon footprint in almost all measures (Figure 1). Only in willow and miscanthus, the compensation is higher than these emissions. The lowest emissions come from the field operations.

Figure 1: Emissions in kg CO₂-eq/ha/year for the average crop rotation, displayed by group of emission sources (Y-axis scale differs per measure).

In the following section, the compensation for energy production is left out of the data in order to have a better comparison of the emission sources. When comparing the relative emissions (Figure 2), it becomes visible that while the field operations related emissions decrease for reduced and no-till, there is an increase in emissions related to production of inputs used. Grassland has the highest field emissions, while willow has the lowest emissions.

Figure 2: Average emissions for groups of emission sources in kg CO₂-eq/ha/year.

As field emissions have such a big influence (for most measures more than 60% of the GHG emissions, Figure 2), they are displayed separately as well for the subgroups (Figure 3). Here, the production of mineral fertilizers has the biggest influence. The lowest emissions for fertilizers on cropland occur when adjusting the crop rotation, after a land use change to willow and miscanthus the emissions from mineral fertilizer are very low too, also the reduced use of chemicals plays a role. Together with no-till and reduced till, these two measures have very low emissions for field preparations compared to the other measures. The emissions from the other measures are relatively similar in terms of farm operations and use of products.

Figure 3: Emissions in kg CO₂-eq/ha/year by subgroup of emissions sources, excluding direct and indirect N₂O soil emissions.

GHG emissions related to fuel for field operations have a relatively low contribution to the total GHG emissions (Figure 2), but the contribution of an operation to the overall emissions differ (Figure 4). Ploughing causes relatively high emissions due to high fuel use, explaining the lower field operation emissions for no-tillage and reduced tillage. For miscanthus and willow, all farm operations are done less often. The harvest for willow, however, is still almost as high as for the annual crops where this operation happens every year.

Figure 4: Field operation (fuel related) emissions in kg CO₂-eq/ha/year.

4.3 Carbon sequestration

According to the RothC simulations for the baseline, the soil has for all three organic matter contents a negative SOC balance, i.e. net CO₂ emissions (

Table 6A). The net emissions can be expected, as this is a sandy soil with intensive crop rotation. With the SOC sequestration measures the emissions decrease, only a land use change to miscanthus leads to an increase of the carbon stock if the initial OM content is low or medium. Also the other measures calculated by means of an EF can reduce the SOC emissions compared to the baseline (

Table 6B). Especially the change to willow leads to a high reduction while the effects of reduced till and agroforestry are low.

Table 6: Soil carbon emissions as modelled by RothC (A) and calculated by means of the EFs (B) for soils low, medium and high in organic matter. Positive numbers are emission, negatives are sequestration..

SOC sequestration measure	SOC emission (kg CO ₂ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)			Absolute change to baseline (kg CO ₂ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)		
	Low OM	Med. OM	High OM	Low OM	Med. OM	High OM
A						
Baseline	1165	1822	2622	0	0	0
Cover crops	53	709	1508	-1111	-1112	-1113
Crop residues	1010	1667	2467	-154	-154	-155
Crop rotation	1063	1684	2439	-102	-138	-182
Grassland	570	1202	1971	-595	-620	-651
Miscanthus	-861	-292	401	-2026	-2114	-2220
B						
Reduced tillage	1043	1665	2415	-122	-157	-207
No till	719	1245	1862	-446	-577	-760
Willow	112	459	825	-1053	-1363	-1797
Agroforestry	1060	1687	2443	-105	-136	-180

When soil carbon is taken into account with the other GHG emissions, miscanthus has the lowest total emissions, followed by willow, cover crops, crop rotation, no till, agroforestry, grassland, reduced till, and finally crop residues (Table 7). For the crop residues and the energy crops the compensation of gas is taken into account here, which is also the reason why incorporation of crop residues results in higher emissions compared to the baseline.

Table 7: Absolute change of emissions compared to the baseline, the values are based on the medium initial SOC content from Table 6. Negative values mean a reduction in emissions compared to the baseline.

SOC sequestration measure	Absolute change of emissions (ton CO ₂ -eq/ha)		
	Other GHG emissions	Soil carbon emissions	Total emissions
Miscanthus	-8.7	-2.1	-10.8
Willow	-3.5	-1.4	-4.8
Cover crops	-0.10	-1.1	-1.2
Crop rotation	-1.0	-0.14	-1.2
No till	-0.05	-0.58	-0.63
Agroforestry	-0.35	-0.14	-0.48
Grassland	0.23	-0.62	-0.39
Reduced tillage	-0.04	-0.16	-0.20
Crop residues	0.69	-0.15	0.54

5 Discussion

Most carbon sequestration measures assessed here lead to a reduction in indirect emissions compared to the baseline. Only when cropland is changed to grassland or crop residues are left on the field, the indirect GHG emissions might increase. However, this increase is fully compensated by the increase in carbon sequestration (section 5.2). Soil N₂O emissions have a substantially higher impact on the overall carbon balance compared to the emissions related to field operations. Also, the substitution of fossil energy by miscanthus or willow has a big influence on the indirect emissions and can lead to a significant reduction of GHG emissions to the atmosphere. However, the land use change might impact food production (section 0) and cropland might be displaced and established in other regions (section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

5.1 Comparison with other studies

The main reason for reduced emissions in no-tillage and reduced tillage was the lower fuel use due to the abandonment of conventional tillage. Increased use of herbicides did not counteract this effect as production and application have much lower emissions, as was also shown in other studies (e.g. Guardia et al., 2016). Sørensen et al. (2014) compared the carbon footprint of reduced and no-tillage systems to conventional tillage. They provide the numbers in g CO₂-eq/kg product, therefore, a direct comparison of numbers is difficult. However, they found an 8.9% reduction for the reduced tillage scenario and for no-tillage 6.5%. These numbers are higher than the reduction found in this assessment, however, they also took carbon sequestration into account. The lower reduction for no-tillage found by the authors was due to a calculated yield reduction of 10%.

While for the tillage scenarios, field operations play a big role, for a change in crop rotation the reduced use of fertilizer has the largest contribution. This was also found by Plaza-Bonilla et al. (2018) who found that 47-62% of external emissions were due to fertilizer use. When a crop was replaced by a legume in their study, they found a decrease by 43% in GHG emissions compared to a crop rotation without legumes, which is similar to the results of our study (-42%). Parajuli et al. (2017) looked at alfalfa for energy production and found a reduced global warming potential compared to spring barley straw, further supporting the reduced emissions found here.

Plaza-Bonilla et al. (2018) also looked at the emissions of including cover crops compared to bare fallow. The decrease they found was 1.2%, which is lower than the 3.9% found here, however, in their study fertilizer was applied to the cover crops and they were already terminated in November, requiring an additional tillage operation.

A high reduction of fertilizer use was found for the energy crops as well. These crops even had negative emissions when taking the reduction in fossil energy emissions into account, which was also found by Styles & Jones (2008). Especially for miscanthus they found larger emission savings because of higher biomass yields compared to willow. Parajuli et al. (2017) analysed, among others, the global warming potential (GWP in kg CO₂-eq/t dry matter) of willow compared to straw for bioenergy. They found a reduction in the GHG emissions by 25% compared to using straw from spring barley. Even though the units are different, this supports the reduced emissions for willow cultivation found here. A reduction

in GHG emissions when changing from arable land to short rotation coppice or perennial grass, including miscanthus, is also confirmed by Harris et al. (2015).

In this assessment, changing silage maize to ryegrass increased the GHG emissions of the crop rotation due to an increased use in fertilizer. This is supported by Parajuli, Kristensen, et al. (2017) who compared the environmental performance of maize, grass-clover, ryegrass and winter-wheat straw for biorefinery. They found an increase by 44% in emissions for ryegrass. This is much higher than the increase found here (Table 4), when only looking at the change from maize to ryegrass, an increase of 29% is calculated in this report. This is partly related to the higher amount of synthetic N fertilizer for ryegrass in that study, which is with 279 kg N/ha almost 100 kg N more than applied to ryegrass in the baseline farm (Table 1), while the mineral N input for maize is similar. However, a fair comparison is difficult as a hectare of grassland produces more protein compared to a hectare of maize, which can reduce the use of concentrates on a farm, and indirectly reduce the import of soybean and its related emissions.

When not taking the substitution of fossil fuels for energy production into account, the emissions in an agroforestry system could be reduced by 8% in this assessment. This reduction is in line with the study from Kanzler et al. (2021) who found a 7% reduction in fossil energy for an alley cropping system with a tree cover of 10% compared to a conventionally managed system. Such a reduction is in line with the expectation that agroforestry should decrease greenhouse gas emissions (Felton et al., 2023).

Contrary to agroforestry, leaving crop residues on the field led in this assessment to an increase in GHG emissions compared to the baseline. This high increase is supported by a study from Cherubini & Ulgiati (2010) who found high GHG emissions savings from using crop residues for bioenergy instead of relying on fossil energy sources. Also Brankatschk & Finkbeiner (2017) underline the importance of considering the use of straw for bioenergy as this can offset GHG emissions of the crop rotation considerably, as was shown in our assessment. However, the effect of increasing SOC sequestration is not yet taken into account.

The comparison with other studies shows that while there are differences in the absolute and relative changes found, the trends are comparable. Many studies also provide numbers for the change in soil organic carbon (SOC) and include it in their assessment to calculate the net GWP, leading to a change in the overall carbon balance (e.g., Parajuli, Knudsen, et al., 2017; Parajuli, Kristensen, et al., 2017; Plaza-Bonilla et al., 2018).

5.2 Soil carbon sequestration

The SOC sequestration measures assessed in this report differ in their potential to sequester carbon as calculated for the baseline farm in this report. Although this is a rough calculation and cannot be easily extrapolated to other farms in Europe, it provides an indication on what the overall potential of a measure is in reducing GHG emissions.

Changes in soil tillage practices had little effect on the other GHG emissions, however, it can improve the SOC balance compared to the baseline more than the practices crop residues or a change in crop rotation. It should be noted, however, that the SOC sequestration calculation is only based on the top 30 cm and that studies have shown that the effect on the whole soil profile can be minimal (Seidel et al., 2024; Haddaway et al., 2017).

Land use change to miscanthus and willow did reduce the other GHG emissions substantially and also increased soil organic carbon compared to the baseline. As this is based on rough calculations, there can be local differences but it can be expected that overall GHG emissions decrease when this measure is applied. For conversion to grassland, the SOC balance is improved compared to the baseline. Conversion of arable land to grassland had higher other GHG emissions compared to other SOC measures, however, the increase in soil carbon lead to lower total emissions compared to the baseline. Besides more organic matter input from grass residues also the increased amount of organic manure applied to the grassland can contribute to the carbon stock changes.

For agroforestry, there was some reduction of other GHG emissions and also the SOC balance was improved. However, since this is only applied to 10% of the land, the change is not substantial, but the overall GHG emissions are at least lower compared to the baseline (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Both crop rotation and crop residue incorporation had minor impact on SOC stocks, as both SOC measures only had an effect in part of the crop rotation (e.g. straw from wheat was incorporated in 1 out of 4 years). Still the net GHG emission reduction is larger for changing the crop rotation by including a legume, as Alfalfa doesn't require N fertilizer, which reduced direct and indirect soil N₂O emissions. Crop residue incorporation was the only SOC measure that had higher net GHG emissions, at least in case when the use of straw for bioenergy production is taken into account (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The increase in soil carbon was not sufficient to the offset the increase due to the loss of substitution of fossil energy. WP2 of Carboseq (Panagea et al., 2023) also showed that only a high share of cereals in the crop rotation positively influenced SOC stocks.

Cover crops, on the other hand, did not result in a large change in the other GHG emissions, however, with 1.1 ton CO₂ per ha of additional SOC sequestration the net mitigation impact was still substantial. Thus, depending on the local circumstances, the cover crops can have a higher mitigation potential compared to other SOC measures, although this will also depend on the type of cover crop and risk on additional N₂O emissions (Porre et al., 2024).

5.3 Effect on food production and land use change

The effects of the SOC measures on can also have impacts on indirect GHG emissions if crop yields change. Reduced yields can lead to conversion of land to cropland elsewhere, which could imply that overall the emissions do not decrease, or to a lesser extent, because the extra land requires extra machinery, inputs and possibly also loss of carbon stocks.

Especially for no-till farming, a yield reduction is often observed, as least during the first years. Pittelkow et al. (2014) for example found in a global meta-analysis that this measure leads to a mean yield reduction of 5.7%. An overview on the effects on crop yield provided by European Commission (2024) showed that most meta-analysis studies found a negative or no-effect on the productivity (7 and 6 studies respectively) while only two reported an increase. Also for reduced tillage, most studies found negative effects on crop yields (European Commission, 2024; Sandén et al., 2018). Considering that no-tillage and reduced tillage only led to a slight reduction in indirect emissions in this assessment, it seems that this measure has the potential to increase overall GHG emissions of the whole agricultural system as the reduced productivity might need to be compensated for elsewhere. Nevertheless, these negative effects might be lowered after a few years as studies have shown that in some systems, no-till can lead to positive effects on productivity in the long term (Sandén et al., 2018; Soane et al., 2012).

The extent of the effect is also highly crop dependent, and some crops might become economically unviable while others stay unaffected (Van den Putte et al., 2010).

Agroforestry, on the other hand, might potentially increase the crop productivity. A study in Switzerland (Sereke et al., 2015) found a land equivalent ratio (LER) of above 1 for many agroforestry systems, meaning that the productivity on 1 ha land was higher than on pure forestry or pure cropland. The same was found by an earlier study which looked at the productivity of agroforestry systems in Spain, France, and the Netherlands (Graves et al., 2007). To conclude that this measure indeed has a positive effect on agroforestry is difficult though because of the scarcity of European studies. The meta-analysis studies analysed by the European Commission (2020), more often showed a positive than negative effect on yield compared to a land use without trees. Thus, a reduction in emissions seems very likely if this measure is adopted, not only on a specific field but also in the whole agricultural system.

Adopting agroforestry can also be a more favourable option to provide biomass for bioenergy compared to changing the whole land to miscanthus or willow cultivation. Willow and miscanthus cropping can reduce the GHG emissions substantially, however, if food demand stays the same, they will not reduce the emissions in the agricultural food sector as the food/feed crops need to be produced elsewhere. This will result in indirect land use change (ILUC), where land is converted elsewhere to compensate for the lost cropland (Czyrnek-Delêtre et al., 2016). The emissions from the indirect land use change can be especially high when forest is converted to cropland (Clarke et al., 2019) and potentially offset the positive effects of bioenergy (Fargione et al., 2008). This is however difficult to assess, and emissions related to ILUC are highly debated in the literature (Czyrnek-Delêtre et al., 2016).

The same might be the case for conversion of cropland to grassland, however, this depends on the kind of crop before grassland conversion. In the arable farm scenario, silage maize was replaced by ryegrass. Both can be used for animal fodder, thus, there is no change in end use. However, the average dry matter yield is often higher for maize compared to ryegrass, Parajuli et al. (2017) report a difference of 12%. Also, when looking at the baseline farms from the Nutri2Cycle project (Duan et al., 2021), the average dry matter yield is 14.5% higher when silage maize is grown compared to ryegrass. However, grass has a higher protein yield compared to silage maize, which could be favourable if a farm is depending on the import of concentrates. A more in-depth analysis would be required to assess the overall impact on food production and net GHG impact for this measure.

Changing the crop rotation to include legumes could have a positive effect on the crop yield, however, many studies also report no effect, especially if the fertilization rate is high (Cernay et al., 2018; Preissel et al., 2015). The same is true for cover crops, most meta-studies reviewed by the European Commission (2022) found no effect on crop productivity. However, some studies also found a negative effect of non-leguminous cover crops on crop productivity.

A change in crop rotation can also lead to a change in land use elsewhere. If a non-leguminous crop is replaced by a legume, but no increase in consumption is taken place, the non-leguminous crop will be grown elsewhere. The positive effects of leguminous crops on indirect farm emissions would then be cancelled out when looking at the complete agricultural system.

The crop residue incorporation measure had higher GHG emissions compared to the baseline. However, many studies also report positive yield effects of this measure (Lehtinen et al., 2014; Lu, 2020). In case of using crop residues for bioenergy, all nutrients are lost, whereas crop residue

incorporation can conserve these nutrient for the following crop. If this is the case, the negative effects of not using the straw for bioenergy production could in this context partly be compensated for by the fact that less land might be needed for the same amount of crop production.

In some countries a high proportion of straw is harvested for usages such as energy production, forage, stall bedding, crop bedding (e.g. strawberries and bulb cultivation), and insulation material (replacing glass fibre and stone wool) (Slier et al., 2022). This means, that if straw remains on the field, more will be removed from somewhere else instead. Thus, SOC sequestration might only be shifted geographically, without leading to a net increase in SOC storage. Also, transport distances might increase, consequently increasing the indirect emissions of this measure further.

5.4 Limitations

The emission factors for field operation and other emission sources used in this study have their uncertainties, as machinery, fuel, or agricultural practices can differ among countries but also among farms within a country. Therefore, the emissions assigned to the different field operations and emission sources show an order of magnitude and trade-offs, but should not be seen as absolute values. In order to obtain reliable numbers, life cycle assessments for selected farms are necessary where all the operations and specific consumptions are quantified.

In this assessment, many assumptions have been made and European or global average values were taken. In the study, a typical Dutch arable farm was used for the baseline, but crop rotations and environmental conditions will differ in other regions. The emissions have only been calculated for one crop rotation. Panagea et al. (2023) showed that the crop residue measure has most effect when cereals are grown in more than 75% but less than 100% of the crop rotation. Such a crop rotation is not common in the Netherlands but might be the case in other countries where this measure then will have a higher potential compared to what we calculated. Also, a different leguminous crop might be chosen for the farm which again would change the overall emissions. Therefore, the same kind of analysis should be repeated for multiple farms in different regions.

The effect of environmental conditions is especially important for the soil carbon sequestration potential. This potential is based on the soil conditions of the specific farm and especially if the clay content is higher, more C could be sequestered than we calculated for the baseline farm that was used. Still the differences compared to the baseline would show similar trends. It should be noted, however, that the carbon sequestration calculated here was based on two different methods. RothC was used to be able to compare the change in soil carbon emissions or sequestration with the baseline. However, this model could not be applied for all measures discussed here. The use of the two different approaches makes it therefore difficult to directly compare between the measures. Calculating the total emissions nevertheless shows whether the carbon emissions can increase the trade-offs or benefits of a measure found by calculating the indirect emissions.

6 Conclusion

This assessment has shown that the potential of SOC sequestration measures to reduce CO₂ in the atmosphere is not endangered by other greenhouse gas emissions. Only the measure cropland conversion to grassland had somewhat higher GHG emissions, due to an increase in mineral fertilizer use compared to arable land. Still the increase in GHG emissions would be compensated by the carbon sequestered in the soil. For the measure incorporation of crop residues (straw) the emissions are also higher, but this is only due to assumption that the straw is no longer available as bioenergy source for the substitution of fossil energy sources. If straw would have been used for other purposes, e.g. bedding material, this would not have been the case.

When not taking the substitution of energy into account, the reduction of fertilizer use has the largest effect across all measures. Such a reduction might for example be achieved by including legumes into the crop rotation, this measure had the highest emission reduction of all cropland management measures. However, such a shift needs be supported with a shift in legume consumption, as otherwise non-leguminous crops grown elsewhere will cancel out the saved N fertilizer. Agroforestry, reduced tillage and no tillage had minor GHG emission reductions.

Some measures, could lead to an increase in indirect GHG emissions because of a reduction in crop productivity, which would be compensated for expansion of cropland elsewhere, i.e. indirect land use change (ILUC). Although these potential ILUC emissions were not quantified, the measures no-till and reduced tillage might lead to lower crop yields, at least on the short term, with potential ILUC impacts. Also conversion of cropland to energy crops might have this risk, although the net impact will very much depend on where or if ILUC will occur.

7 References

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Appendix A

Table A1: Factors and conversions to assess the other GHG emissions from SOC sequestration measures

Operation	Crop	Emission (kg CO ₂ - eq/ha)	Cons- umption	Unit and source consumption	Conversion factor consumption	Unit and conversion consumption
"Normal" crop planting	Default	11.7	11.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Crop harvest	Default	114.8	33.3	kg fuel/ha/yr [1]	3.447	[1]
Fertilization N ₂ O	Maize	1319	198.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.025	kg N ₂ O/kg N [6]
Fertilization N ₂ O	Potato	1879	282.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.025	kg N ₂ O /kg N [6]
Fertilization N ₂ O	Sugar beet	1412	212.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.025	kg N ₂ O /kg N [6]
Fertilization N ₂ O	Wheat	999	150.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.025	kg N ₂ O /kg N [6]
Fertilization N ₂ O	Grass	2325	349.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.025	kg N ₂ O /kg N [6]
Fertilizer application M	Default	3.3	3.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Fertilizer application S	Default	27.9	27.9	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Fertilizer M	Maize	478	138.0	kg N/ha [4]	3.461	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg N [10]
Fertilizer M	Potato	491	142.0	kg N/ha [4]	3.461	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg N [10]
Fertilizer M	Sugar beet	491	142.0	kg N/ha [4]	3.461	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg N [10]
Fertilizer M	Wheat	519	150.0	kg N/ha [4]	3.461	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg N [10]
Fertilizer M	Grass	637	184.0	kg N/ha [4]	3.461	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg N [10]
Fungicide	Maize	0.0	0.0	kg/ha/yr [3]	14.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]
Fungicide	Potato	117	8.2	kg/ha/yr [3]	14.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]
Fungicide	Sugar beet	5.7	0.4	kg/ha/yr [3]	14.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]
Fungicide	Wheat	8.6	0.6	kg/ha/yr [3]	14.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]
Fungicide	grass and alfalfa	2.9	0.2	kg/ha/yr [3]	14.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]
Gas	Wheat	-2841	58.4	GJ/ha straw [4,7]	-48.7	kg- CO ₂ -eq/GJ [7]
Gas	Miscanthus	-7625	156.6	GJ/ha/yr [9]	-48.7	kg- CO ₂ -eq/GJ [7]
Gas	Willow	-2119	43.5	GJ/ha/yr [9]	-48.7	kg- CO ₂ -eq/GJ [7]

Operation	Crop	Emission (kg CO ₂ -eq/ha)	Consumption	Unit and source consumption	Conversion factor consumption	Unit and conversion consumption
Herbicide	Maize	25.4	1.1	kg/ha/yr [3]	23.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Herbicide	Potato	85.5	3.7	kg/ha/yr [3]	23.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Herbicide	Sugar beet	78.5	3.4	kg/ha/yr [3]	23.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Herbicide	Wheat	9.2	0.4	kg/ha/yr [3]	23.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Herbicide	grass and alfalfa	11.6	0.5	kg/ha/yr [3]	23.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Insecticide	Maize	0.0	0.0	kg/ha/yr [3]	18.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Insecticide	Potato	3.7	0.2	kg/ha/yr [3]	18.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Insecticide	Sugar beet	0.0	0.0	kg/ha/yr [3]	18.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Insecticide	Wheat	0.0	0.0	kg/ha/yr [3]	18.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Insecticide	grass and alfalfa	0.0	0.0	kg/ha/yr [3]	18.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Miscanthus harvest	Miscanthus	17.7	5.1	kg fuel/ha/yr [2]	3.447	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Miscanthus planting	Miscanthus	1.8	0.5	kg fuel/ha/yr [2]	3.447	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Moldboard plough	Default	55.7	55.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [2]		[1]
NO ₃ leaching	Maize	195	42.5	kg N/ha [4]	0.017	[6]
NO ₃ leaching	Potato	243	53.1	kg N/ha [4]	0.017	Kg C-eq/kg seed [6]
NO ₃ leaching	Sugar beet	363	79.2	kg N/ha [4]	0.017	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
NO ₃ leaching	Wheat	460	100.4	kg N/ha [4]	0.017	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
NO ₃ leaching	Grass	45.8	10.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.017	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
No-till crop planting	Default	13.9	13.9	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Pesticide application	Default	5.1	5.1	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Potato planting	Potato	25.3	25.3	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Seed production	Default	5.5	12.5	kg seeds/ha [11]	0.120	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [5]
Silage harvest	Silage	20.7	6.0	kg fuel/ha/yr [2]	3.45	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg [1]
Straw removal	Wheat	16.7	16.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Straw transport	Wheat	8.8	4.0	t straw/ha [4]	0.044	kg CO ₂ -eq/tkm [1,8]

Operation	Crop	Emission (kg CO ₂ - eq/ha)	Consumption	Unit and source consumption	Conversion factor consumption	Unit and conversion consumption
Stubble cultivation	Default	14.7	14.7	kg CO ₂ -eq/ha [1]		[1]
Willow harvest	Willow	92.1	26.7	kg fuel/ha/yr [2]	3.45	[1]
Willow planting	Willow	1.4	0.4	kg fuel/ha/yr [2]	3.45	[1]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization M	Maize	40.2	138.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization M	Potato	41.4	142.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization M	Sugar beet	41.4	142.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization M	Wheat	43.7	150.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization M	Grass	53.6	184.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization S	Maize	17.5	60.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization S	Potato	40.8	140.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization S	Sugar beet	20.4	70.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization S	Wheat	0.0	0.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]
Vol. N ₂ O Fertilization S	Grass	48.1	165.0	kg N/ha [4]	0.001	kg N ₂ O /kgN [6]

[1] (Lal, 2004), [2] (Clarke et al., 2019), [3] CBS Nederland, [4] (Duan et al., 2018), [5] (Plaza-Bonilla et al., 2018), [6] (Hergoual'c'h et al., 2019), [7] (Slier et al., 2022), [8] (Timonen et al., 2019), [9] (Styles & Jones, 2008), [10] (Brentrup et al., 2018), [11] (Cotswold Seeds, 2024)